

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard

Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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Versions

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Method responsible: Sebastien Moreau/Jacqueline Stefels

1 Description of sampling gear

Biological sampling of sea-ice protist is done by collecting ice cores. Ice cores should be collected using a 0.09 m (inner diameter) core barrel (Kovacs Enterprise Mark II, USA) attached to either a hand corer or, ideally, a power drill. Researchers should work together in teams of 3-4 to collect and process ice cores. Responsibilities within the team should be clearly identified and all equipment and sample containers should be prepared and packed before arrival on station. It is essential that sampling containers are well labeled and organized before coring begins. Coring locations should be decided on upon arrival on site, with care taken not to walk over or disrupt the designated sampling location. Follow all safety protocols as prescribed by research vessel.

Processing of several samples taken ice cores will include chemical use. A list of the necessary chemicals and their corresponding parameter is provided below. It is the responsibility of the individual using the chemical and processing the sample to operate in a manner that is safe for themselves, others on the ship, and the environment being sampled. Safety Data Sheets (SDS) should be readily available in the labs and safety procedures as prescribed by the research vessel should be adhered to, including locked chemical storage cabinets and designated workspaces for radioisotopes.

Chemical	Parameter	Safety consideration
Saturated mercury chloride (HgCl ₂)	DIC and CH ₄	Highly toxic
Methanol	Chlorophyll a	Carcinogenic
Glutaraldehyde	Taxonomy and flow cytometry	Carcinogenic
Formaldehyde	Taxonomy	Carcinogenic and mutagenic
Hydrochloric acid (HCl)	Several	Corrosive
Ethanol	Several	Toxic
NaOH	DMSP	corrosive

2 Sampling gear deployment

2.1 Deployment:

- Ensure all equipment is ready, including core barrel, drill, shovel, saw, cutting board, sampling containers, notebook, gloves, measuring stick, ice thickness tape, ice auger, light measurement equipment, etc.
- Choose the coring location. In the field notebook, take note of basic weather and time observations including cloud cover and time of day.
- Prepare for the first ice core by taking 3 measurements of the snow depth 8 cm equidistant from each other (in a triangle with 8 cm sides) using a measuring stick. Note down snow measurements in the field notebook.
- Remove snow over the coring location using a shovel. Then start drilling the ice core with the Kovacs corer and drill. Ideally, one person is responsible for coring and does not touch the core at all while another person has “clean hands” and wears vinyl gloves to extract the core from the barrel, measure, and cut it.
- When ice core is retrieved, bring it to the cutting board. The cutting board should be set-up in a shaded location, for example a tent or in the shade of a cooler/box, and the ice core should be exposed to as little light as possible. The person in charge of cutting measures and notes down the core length before cutting the core. The cutting scheme should be decided on before the station, and a standard cutting scheme for biological ice cores is 0-5 cm, 5-10 cm, 10-20 cm and 20 cm sections and a standard cutting scheme for physical and chemical cores is every 10 cm. Zero on the ice core represents the ice-snow interface.
- Proceed in this way until all the way through the ice, using extensions for coring if necessary.
- Take ice thickness and free board measurements at the core hole after extraction of the core using the ice thickness tape.

2.2 Calibration:

Follow calibration procedures for the on-ice thermometer and salinometer that will be used in the lab following sampling. For the on-ice thermometer we recommend a Testo 720 temperature meter, see [here](#) for instrument information and a detailed manual. For a salinometer, we recommend a WTW ProfiLine Cond 3110, [here](#) is instrument information and a detailed manual.

2.3 Post-Deployment

Once all on-ice measurements have been taken (ice cores, light, under-ice water, plankton nets), bring samples back to the ship for post-processing. Ice core sections for biological parameters should be pooled together and immediately diluted with filtered seawater at a 3:1 volumetric ratio for buffered melt. Buffered melt should take place in cool, dark conditions, e.g., in cooler jugs. For buffered melt, use seawater filtered through a 0.2 μm filter. The melted sea ice and filtered seawater solution can then be subsampled for all desired biological parameters, where measurements represent an average response of the bottom-ice community at that particular sampling location. Remember to freshwater rinse all equipment after sampling and MiliQ rinse melt containers between stations. Also remember to take final volume measurements of all ice core + FSW solutions before further sampling (i.e., filtration).

2.4 Common Issues

Well organized and intuitive log sheets and labeling systems should be used commonly throughout the cruise. Ice core sampling plan including core division, roles, order of cores/sampling etc. should be discussed and decided on before station. The sea-ice biologists and physicists should discuss parameters interesting to both parties beforehand (i.e., temperature, salinity, microstructure, inorganic nutrients, etc.) to avoid double sampling. The number of cores taken per sample should be decided based on the volume needed for desired parameters/experiments. Keep in mind that a larger number of biological cores requires higher volumes of FSW. Preparing FSW for an ice station can be time consuming, set up a peristaltic pump and prepare FSW before sampling as much as possible. A suggested workflow is outlined below with a table including the number of ice cores needing to be sampled and corresponding parameters. Note that ice coring, water sampling, and net sampling can occur in parallel by small working groups (2-4 people each).

2.5 Workflow suggestion

- Upon arrival at the ice station, note time, position, and weather conditions. Decide coring location.
- Set-up for ice coring, delineate coring location and ask others NOT to walk over coring site.
- Take light measurements using under-ice arm and LI-COR tripod.
- Take temperature core, making temperature measurements using drill and thermometer. Work quickly to avoid warming of core.
- Take all other ice cores, sectioning into appropriate sections along the way.
- Take under-ice water samples.
- Take net samples.

Core name	Number of cores	Parameter(s) measured	Post processing
Temperature core	1	Temperature	Processed immediately on the ice using thermometer
Physics 1	1	Microstructure	Bagged whole, taken on board and stored at -20C
Physics 2	1	Density	Bagged whole, taken on board and stored at -20C
Chemistry core	1	Salinity, d180, inorganic nutrients, DOC	Cut into 10 cm sections and placed into pre-labelled containers for unbuffered melt (i.e., no added FSW)
DIC core	1	DIC	Cut into 10 cm sections and placed in vacuum

			sealed bags for gas-tight melt
Bio core 1	3	Chl <i>a</i> , POC/PON, EPS, and biogenic silica	Cut following the biological sectioning scheme and bring onto ship for buffered melt (3:1 ratio with FSW) and post-processing (i.e., filtering and fixation)
Bio core 2	1	Ice algae taxonomy, flow cytometry, and microscopy, DMSP	Cut following the biological sectioning scheme, keep in the dark!, bring back into ship for buffered melt (3:1 ratio with FSW) and post-processing
Bio core 3	4	Primary production measurements (oxygen optode PI curve incubations)	Cut using desired sectioning scheme, keep in the dark!, bring back into ship for buffered melt (3:1 ratio with FSW) and post-processing
Bio core 4	3	Ice algal culturing	Scrape off the bottom 1 cm of the ice core where the algae is most concentrated and place into sample container. This will make a highly concentrated sample for culturing of ice algae.

3 Sample sorting-collection-preservation procedure: Protist sampling from sea ice

Samples related to protist/biological sampling in sea ice are described below in individual sub-chapters.

3.1 Temperature

- Temperature measurements are to be taken on the ice immediately after recovery of the first sea-ice core collected at each station.
- Take measurements in drill holes about 0.05 m deep and at 0.05 m spacing along a sea-ice core using a previously calibrated Testo-720 thermometer (Testo, Germany)
- Make sure to note each temperature measurement in the field notebook

3.2 Salinity

- Salinity measurements are to be taken from undiluted melted ice core sections (chemistry core). We suggest sectioning every 0.10 m and melting undiluted in cool, dark conditions.
- Bulk salinity can be measured using a pre-calibrated Profiline Cond 3110 portable conductivity meter (WTW, Germany).

3.3 Stable oxygen isotopes

- Ratios of ^{16}O to ^{18}O ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) in the H_2O molecule are measured to a very high accuracy. Samples of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ are collected to determine the fractions of river meteoric meltwater and sea-ice meltwater in the ocean. This sample is not related to dissolved oxygen concentration.
- From the undiluted melt (chemistry core), sample rinse a 20 mL scintillation vial and cap three times.
- Fill the vial with sample completely, creating a convex meniscus.
- Carefully apply the cap and check for small air bubble, between 2 and 5mm.

- When all $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples have been collected, dry the vials, tighten the caps and seal with Parafilm.
- Store $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples at room temperature or in a fridge, avoid freezing.

3.4 Inorganic nutrients

- Prior to the cruise, acid wash 40 mL amber vials by soaking in 10% HCl+Mili Q solution overnight and rinsing thoroughly with MiliQ (triple rinse) and drying at 50C until completely dry. Then burn the bottles at 450C for 6 hours. Acid wash the lids for about 30 minutes (less robust to the acid) and dry them at 50C until completely dry. Store clean vials and lids in a new Ziploc bag that's been triple rinsed with MiliQ and dried completely. Then carefully pack in boxes to prevent damage and clearly label for packing and shipment.
- Assemble a swinnex with a pre-combusted GF/F filter. Place syringe into undiluted melt (chemistry core) and take up a small amount of sample to rinse the syringe. Repeat three times.
- Take up a full syringe of sample (about 60 mL), push out air, and attach swinnex. Using steady but light pressure, gently push sample through the filter at a drip-drip-drip speed. Rinse the filter with sample, and then rinse the sampling vial and cap with filtered sample 3 times.
- Fill sampling vial with filtered sample, leaving a small amount of headspace such that the sample can expand when freezing without spilling out or damaging the vial.
- Store samples at -20°C.

3.5 Dissolved organic carbon (DOC)

- Prior to the cruise, acid wash 40 mL amber vials by soaking in 10% HCl+Mili Q solution overnight and rinsing thoroughly with MiliQ (triple rinse) and drying at 50C until completely dry. Then burn the bottles at 450C for 6 hours. Acid wash the lids for about 30 minutes (less robust to the acid) and dry them at 50C until completely dry. Store clean vials and lids in a new Ziploc bag that's been triple rinsed with MiliQ and dried completely. Then carefully pack in boxes to prevent damage and clearly label for packing and shipment.
- Set up a clean working space and use vinyl gloves. Acid wash sampling vials (20 mL scintillation vials), syringes, and swinnex before sampling. Rinse sampling vials, syringes, and swinnex with MiliQ after acid bath and before use.

- Assemble a swinnex with a pre-combusted GF/F filter. Place syringe into undiluted melt (chemistry core) and take up a small amount of sample to rinse the syringe. Repeat three times.
- Take up a full syringe of sample (about 60 mL), push out air, and attach swinnex. Using steady but light pressure, gently push sample through the filter at a drip-drip-drip speed. Rinse the filter with sample, and then rinse the sampling vial and cap with filtered sample 3 times.
- Fill each vial to just below the lid, acidify with 100 μL 2N HCl and place lid. Cover lids with parafilm.
- Store in the fridge (+4C) and dark.

3.6 Dissolved inorganic carbon / total alkalinity (DIC/TA)

- Leave the vacuum sealed 10 cm core sections from the DIC core to melt in dark conditions.
- Using a peristaltic pump, carefully transfer the melted ice core into a clean 250 mL borosilicate bottle, being careful to avoid bubble formation.
- Overfill the sampling bottle 1-2 volumes for rinsing and removal of air bubbles. Carefully remove the tube and turn off the pump.
- Spike the sample with 60 μL saturated mercuric chloride (HgCl_2) to each sample by submerging the pipette tip into the sample. Close the bottle with the blue cap. Do not shake or mix.
- Store samples at +4C in the dark.

3.7 Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS)

- Take a pre-determined volume of sample (20-200 mL) from the FSW + ice core melt solution labelled as Bio Core 1. The volume taken depends on total volume of sample and amount of biomass in core.
- Filter sample onto 25 mm polycarbonate filters (0.4 μm pore size) under low vacuum pressure, taking care to use a glass filter funnel for filtration in order to get the proper seal with the polycarbonate filter.
- Carefully fold filter in half, with sample protected inside, using forceps. Place folded sample in a tinfoil pouch and store at -20°C.

3.8 Particulate organic carbon / nitrogen (POC/PON)

- Take a pre-determined volume of sample from the FSW + ice core melt solution labelled as Bio Core 1. Volume taken for POC/PON should be about twice that taken for Chl *a* (see section 3.9). Sample volume should be determined based on the amount of biomass in the water column. Generally, POC filters should have a light but noticeable color to them after filtration.
- Filter sample onto pre-combusted 25 mm GF/F filters. Filters should be combusted at 450°C for 12 hours before the cruise. Store the tinfoil-wrapped filters in a well labeled box or ziplock bag.
- Remember to gently mix the bottle by inverting three times to ensure that particles are suspended before filtering. Also ensure that the mesh side of the filter is facing up on the filter holder, not the soft waves side (back side).
- Filter under low vacuum pressure (about -30 kPa) and cover the funnels with aluminum foil when filtering. Rinse the funnel with filtered seawater once the sample has been filtered. Take care not to let the filters dry out, which can cause damage to the filters and result in particle loss.
- After filtration, use forceps to carefully place GF/F into Pall filter slides. Place slides into oven set at 60°C and allow them to fully dry (about 24 hours).
- Store samples at room temperature. Wrap together filter slides from one station in aluminum foil and keep them in a labelled Ziploc bag.
- Prepare a reference filter (blank) for each station by filtering filtered seawater onto a pre-combusted filter. The reference filter will get a normal running number, so make sure to make a note on the CTD log sheet to avoid confusion with numbering on following casts.

3.9 Chlorophyll *a*

- Take a pre-determined volume of sample from the FSW + ice core melt solution labelled as Bio Core 1. Volume taken is dependent on biomass present (a light color on the filter is enough)
- Filter sample onto 25 mm GF/F filters. Remember to gently mix the bottle by inverting three times to ensure that particles are suspended before filtering. Also ensure that the mesh side of the filter is facing up on the filter holder, not the soft waves side (back side).

- Filter under low vacuum pressure (about -30 kPa) and cover the funnels with aluminum foil when filtering. Rinse the funnel with filtered seawater once the sample has been filtered. Take care not to let the filters dry out.
- Use forceps to lift the filters into plastic tubes for extraction.
- Add 5 mL of methanol to the extraction tubes, close with lid, and cover with aluminum foil to block light. Place in refrigerator (dark, +4C).
- Allow pigments to extract into methanol for at least 12 hours. 18 hours extraction time is optimal, and filters can extract for up to 24 hours, but beyond that pigment degradation can occur. Make sure to note the start and end time of extraction, before measuring Chl-a with a fluorometer.
- Rinse filtration funnels and manifold with freshwater between stations.

3.10 Biogenic silica

- Take a pre-determined volume of sample from the FSW + ice core melt solution labelled as Bio Core 1. Volume taken depends on biomass present.
- Filter sample (depending on diatom biomass present) onto a polycarbonate membrane filter (0.8 μm pore size, 25 mm diameter) under low vacuum pressure (-30 kpa).
- Place filter into prelabelled plastic petri dish and place in oven at +60°C to dry, leaving petri dish slightly open to allow for evaporation.
- Once filters are dry (ca. 24 hours in the oven), seal petri dishes with parafilm and wrap filter slides from one station together in aluminum foil. Place in labelled Ziploc bag and store at room temperature.
- Prepare a reference filter (blank) for each sampling event by filtering a similar volume of filtered seawater onto a filter and treating it the same as the samples.

3.11 Ice algae taxonomy

- Decant (around) 90 mL of sample from Bio Core 2 into a pre-labelled 100 mL brown glass (or plastic) bottle).
- Under the fume hood, add 0.5 mL of 25% glutaraldehyde and allow to fix for approx. 5 min. Thereafter add 5 mL of 20% hexamine-buffered formaldehyde. The final concentration is 0.1% glutaraldehyde and 1% formaldehyde in a 100 mL solution.

- Store the samples at +4C in the dark. Do not freeze.

3.12 Flow cytometry

- Rinse a 50 mL falcon tube three times with sample filtered through a 40 µm cell strainer. Then fill the falcon tube with about 40 mL of filtered sample. Use sample from Bio Core 2.
- Pipette 1.8 mL of filtered sample into 2 mL cryovials in triplicate (3 per depth)
- Under the fume hood, add 38 µl of 25% glutaraldehyde into each cryovial.
- Fix the samples for 2 hours in the fridge and then snap freeze in -80°C.
- Store samples in cryobox at -80°C.

3.13 Net community production using O₂ optodes

- Set up computer system, chambers, and water circulator on work bench. It is smart to divide the work bench into dry and wet areas as the electronic equipment must not get wet. Assess everything for damage and potential leaks and check computer system and probe life. Ensure everything is secure with tape and straps.
- Arrange LED lamp adjacent to clear wall on chamber.
- Arrange the clear bottles in the chamber and label consecutively from position one to position nine, with the first position marking the bottle closest to the light (i.e., the clear chamber wall). The bottle at position ten (farthest from the light) should be prepared with black electrical tape to prevent any light from entering in the bottle and will be used as the dark control.
- Add magnetic stir bars to each bottle.
- Using a peristaltic pump with nitex covering the outflow to remove any large grazers, fill bottles with sample from the bottom up. Use ice core melt + FSW solution from Bio Core 3. Mix sample before filling bottles.
- Overfill bottles to prevent formation of a headspace. There must be no bubbles in the bottle once the stopper is placed.
- Cover the clear wall of the chamber with foil and place bottles into pre-cooled and darkened chamber for equilibration (2-3 hours minimum).

- Calibrate optode sensors immediately prior to each incubation using a 0% and 100% dissolved oxygen standards of 0.17 M sodium dithionite ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$) and air saturated water (bubbled FSW for more than 10 minutes), respectively. This accounts for any sensor drift or photodegradation that may have occurred with extended use. The calibration solutions should be made fresh before each incubation.
- Once calibrated and equilibrated, fit each bottle with an optode sensor, taking care not to pull the optodes up/down during placement or incubation to avoid volume displacement and inaccurate measurements.
- Incubate samples for 24-70 hours under continuous illumination and mixing. The 1 cm magnetic stir bars should be set to about 60 rpm. The oxygen concentration is recorded for each bottle at about 2 s time intervals throughout the entire incubation period.
- To stop incubation, turn off optodes and remove from bottles. Measure average PAR using handheld PAR sensor at each bottle position by replacing optodes with PAR probe.
- Pool all samples after incubation (except dark bottles) and filter for additional chlorophyll measurement. An additional nutrient sample can also be taken in order to determine net nutrient uptake (if done, a nutrient sample must also be taken at T0 from bulk sample). Rinse optodes with MilliQ and gently blot dry with Kim wipe to prevent salt damage and corrosion. Rinse incubation bottles three times with FSW after each incubation.

3.14 Ice algae culturing

- Set-up LED strip lights in a section of a refrigerator (+4°C) by taping the LED onto the inner walls or shelving. Adjust the lighting to a very very low setting to force slow growth and prevent nutrient limitation.
- Use a 0.2 μm sealed filter and a sterile 60 mL syringe.
- Place syringe into F2 media bottle and draw up media. Hold the cap to the media bottle while you're doing this step to avoid contamination of the cap.
- Place filter onto syringe and filter media into a new and sterile culture flask (60 mL Falcon flask, for example).
- Place re-filtered media into the fridge to cool.

- Transfer ice scrapes from Bio Core 4 into the cooled culture flasks, taking care not to touch the inside of the flask. Seal with cap.
- Place the culture flask back in the fridge as soon as possible after transfer. If possible, lay the flask horizontally so there is a larger surface area for the algae to grow on.

3.15 Transmitted and incident irradiance measurements

- Program the LI-COR LI-1500 logger before arrival site visit/station for efficiency. The logger can be programmed with the provided sensor calibration, which is unique to each sensor used. Sensor calibrations are provided for measurement in air or water (i.e., under the ice), and each must be used separately for surface or transmitted measurements.
- Calibration data is entered to the logger by selecting MENU > Sensors > Add New Sensor and selecting the model number LI-COR LI-193. A sensor out of calibration warning will appear if more than two years have passed since the date of the sensor's last calibration. The sensor must be sent back to the LI-COR factory for re-calibration. Double check that the sensor is satisfactorily calibrated before the cruise.
- Calibration information can be found online by searching for the sensor's serial number at [CALIBRATION](#). All necessary calibration data must be entered for the sensor being used.
- Detailed information about settings and configurations on the logger can be found online at [LI-COR](#).
- Mark out the area to be used for coring and (e.g., with flags/bamboo sticks). Take caution to NOT WALK over the sampling area. A pristine snow cover is required for representative light measurements.
- Assemble the underwater arm and attach the LI-COR LI-193 spherical underwater quantum sensor. Make sure cable ends do not get wet and take caution not to damage the sensor. Turn on the logger and double check the configurations.
- Briefly, the input selected on the logger should correspond to the input port where the LI-COR LI-192 sensor is attached. Take care to select air or water depending on which measurement is being taken, and that configuration is "Active" in the menu settings. Settings for these steps can be found by selecting MENU > Configurations > Add New Config.
- Take snow measurements and then make a hole using the 10 inch auger. The hole should be made at the north side of the sampling area such that the deployed arm (which is 1.5 m out from the deployment hole) will be positioned facing south and will be in the center of the 3 x 3 m area.

- Then insert the underwater arm in the auger hole with a LICOR sensor attached and pull on the string to position it upwards. Turn the sensor towards the sun and position it roughly 10 cm below the ice bottom by carefully bringing the sensor up until it lightly touches the ice, and then lower it 10 cm from that position.
- Select the channel for measurements in water on the logger (should be pre-programmed before arrival on site).
- Note down 3 to 5 measurements from the LICOR sensor. This represents integrated incident downwelling irradiance transmitting beneath the ice-water interface. Take note of variable weather conditions between measurements and these can have a big impact on reliable transmittance data.
- Remember to freshwater rinse equipment after sampling.
- Sea ice cores for any bio-optical calibrations (e.g. remote estimation of sea ice algal biomass) should be taken proximal-to the sensor location under the ice (i.e. in the center of the 3m x 3m sampling area)
- Select the channel for measurements in air on the logger (should be pre-programmed before arrival on site).
- To measure incident upwelling (albedo) and downwelling irradiance above the snow surface, attach the LI-COR LI-192 quantum sensor to a 1 m pole that is held level and approximately 1 m above the snow surface and facing the sun. A tripod set-up is optimal. Make sure to position yourself below the sensor to not create shadows.
- Note down 3 to 5 measurements with the sensor facing upwards and 3 to 5 measurements more with the spectrometer facing downwards. This represents the incident downwelling irradiance and incident upwelling irradiance above the snow surface, respectively.
- Also take note of weather conditions during measurements, which can have a big impact on reliable transmittance data. Take note of the cloud cover and how it is changing.
- If sampling at the same sites consistently over a campaign, light measurements should be taken at a consistent time of day (e.g., always in the morning or always at noon or...).

3.16 Dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP)

- DMSP is a volatile and relatively insoluble trace gas and the concentration in the sample will be affected by prolonged contact with air. Therefore, sample with care.
- Prelabel the sample bottles prior to sampling.
- Take 10mL from each depth horizon and pipet directly in a 20 mL glass DMSP-vial. Add 50 μ L of a 2.3 μ M D3-DMSP working solution for standard additions.
- Add 1 pellet of NaOH and close firmly. Label appropriately and store upright in -20°C

3.17 Net community production by recording uptake of the ^{13}C stable isotope.

- Start the experiment by adding 2 ml ^{13}C -NaHCO₃ from a stock solution (1 gram ^{13}C -HCO₃ + 20 ml MQ) to ca. 2L of the melted sea ice.
- Mix the tracer by gently shaking the bottle. This is important!
- Take t₀ samples
 - DIC: fill a 8ml amber bottle to the top. Store at 4°C.
 - DMSP: use a 10ml pipet for 3 x 10ml in 20ml screw-top vials + 1 pellet NaOH. Store at -20°C.
 - Chl.a: filter ca. 20ml; for further details see protocol
- From the Nalgene bottle, transfer 250ml to 6 tissue culture flasks.
- Arrange LED lamp adjacent to clear wall on chamber (see protocol for O₂ optodes.
- Arrange the tissue flasks and label consecutively from position one to position six, with the first position marking the bottle closest to the light (i.e., the clear chamber wall) in a pre-cooled and darkened chamber. The bottle at position six (farthest from the light) should be prepared with black electrical tape to prevent any light from entering in the bottle and will be used as the dark control.
- Incubate samples for 8-10 hours under continuous illumination. Gentle shake the flasks every hour

- To stop incubation, take the samples from the experiment in a fixed consecutive order for filtration. Make sure to note the time. Prepare and label alu foil before filtration.
- Depending on the biomass 50-200ml is filtered over 2.5cm pre-combusted GFF Whatman filters using a low vacuum pressure (-30 kpa) under dim light conditions. Fold the filter 1x, pack in alu foil and flash freeze in LN2.
- Store at -20°C
- Complete the meta-sheet.

4 Sample analysis method

4.1 Temperature

- Temperature measurements will be taken on the ice. No further analysis is needed.

4.2 Salinity

- Salinity will be measured aboard R/V Polarstern using, for example, a pre-calibrated Profiline Cond 3110 portable conductivity meter (WTW, Germany). No further analysis is needed.

4.3 Stable oxygen isotopes

- Samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ should be stored and shipped to Vrije Universiteit, Brussels, Belgium for analysis on a Perspective isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Nu Instrument, Ametek) coupled to a Gas Bench system. All samples should also be standardized against V-SMOW.

4.4 Inorganic nutrients

- Samples for inorganic nutrients should be stored at -20C (see section 3.4) and shipped to UiT the Arctic University of Norway for analysis on a QuAatro Autoanalyzer (SEAL Analytical Ltd, Wrexham, United Kingdom).

4.5 Dissolved organic carbon

- Samples for DOC should be stored and shipped to the UiT the Arctic University of Norway for analysis on a Shimadzu ASI-V/TOC-V analyzer.

4.6 Dissolved inorganic carbon / total alkalinity

- Samples for DIC/TA should be stored and shipped to the Institute of Marine Research in Tromsø, Norway for analysis using potentiometric titration with 0.1N hydrochloric acid on a Versatile Instrument for the Determination of Titration Alkalinity (VINDTA 3D, Marianda, Germany).

4.7 Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS)

- Samples for EPS should be stored and shipped to UiT the Arctic University of Norway for analysis on a UV-Vis spectrophotometer and following the phenol-extraction protocol of Dubois et al., 1956 (Dubois, M. and Gilles, K. A. and Hamilton, J. K. and Rebers, P. A. and Smith, F., 1956:1402659, Journal article, 28, Analytical Chemistry, (350–356), Colorimetric method for determination of sugars and related substances., (1956)).

4.8 Particulate organic carbon/nitrogen

- Samples for POC/PON should be prepared for analysis by acidifying in fuming hydrochloric acid for ca. 12 hours before packing into tin capsules.
- After fumigation and packing, samples will be sent to Vrije Universiteit, Brussels, Belgium for measurement with an element analyzer (EA, Eurovector, Italy) coupled to an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Horizon IRMS, Nu Instruments, United Kingdom).

4.9 Chlorophyll *a*

- Chl *a* samples can be processed on ship using a Turner Trilogy Fluorometer (Turner Designs, USA) following the steps outlined below.
- Turn fluorometer on at least 10 min and allow samples to warm to room temperature before taking first measurement.
- Fill 10 mm cuvette with methanol and dry on the outside with a KimTech wipe, place in cuvette holder inside the fluorometer and take measurement. This is the pre-analysis blank measurement.
- After taking first blank, transfer sample into a new 10 mm cuvette and dry on the outside with a KimTech wipe. Place in fluorometer and take measurement. Read the value and note down as R_b value (before acid addition). If sample is too concentrated dilute with methanol, making sure to note down dilution.

- Take the cuvette out of the fluorometer and add 2-3 drops of 5% HCl, cover the cuvette with parafilm and mix gently by inverting 3 times. Wait 30 seconds to allow reaction to complete and take a new measurement. This is the Ra value (after acid addition).
- Take measurements in this way for all samples, and then take a final blank measurement.
- Dispose sample after readings into designated methanol waste container.
- Fluorometer should be calibrated before or after the cruise with Chl *a* extract to derive calibration constants noted down for calculation of Chl *a* and phaeopigments on Excel.

4.10 Biogenic silica

- Samples for the determination of the biogenic and lithogenic silica should be stored and shipped to the University of Brest, France for analysis following the NaOH/HF digestion method of de Master (1981).

4.11 Ice algal taxonomy

- Samples for taxonomic analysis should be stored and shipped to the Institute of Oceanology, Poland using light microscopy.
- Samples should be sedimented for 20-40 hours before analysis following the Utermohl method.
- Taxa identification should be done based on morphological characteristics following e.g., Johansen and Fryxell (1985), Thomas (1997), Scott and Marchant (2005), and the online repository at the World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org/index.php>).

4.12 Flow cytometry

- Samples for flow cytometry should be stored and shipped at -80C to UiT for analysis on a flow cytometer.

4.13 Net community production using O₂ optodes

- Optode incubation data will be stored on the associated computer and should be backed up on at least one other location. No other processing is required.

4.14 Ice algal culturingii

- Samples for ice algal culturing should be delivered to the MicrSiO laboratory at UiT the Arctic University of Norway for further growth and eventual experimentation.

4.15 DMSP

- Pre-label glass storage bottles before starting sample preparation
- DMSP: From each amber bottle, pipette very accurately (!) 10 mL into a 20 mL DMSP-vial with a 10 mL plastic pipet and a red pipetting balloon. You do not need to change pipettes for every sample (save the environment!!), but can use one pipet for all samples of one sampling day. In between each sample: rinse with milli-Q, followed by a few mL of the next sample.
- Add 50 μ L of a 2.3 μ M D3-DMSP working solution.
- Add a pellet of NaOH and close firmly with a screw cap (wearing lab gloves improves the grip on the caps!).
- store at -20°C.

4.16 Particulate organic carbon – 13C

- Samples for production analysis will be sent to the University of Groningen for analyses with Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy analyser (CM-CRDS, with a G2101-I Analyzer, Picarro, California, USA).